

The Influence of Work-Family Conflict and Job Satisfaction on Turnover Intention with Organizational Commitment as a Mediation Variable in Bebek Tepi Sawah Employees Restaurant Ubud

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to determine the influence of work-family conflict and job satisfaction on turnover intention with organizational commitment as a mediating variable in Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees. The sample in this study included all employees of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud. The number of samples in this study was 62 people. Testing the research hypothesis uses the Partial Least Square (PLS) application. The results of this research show that: (1) Work family conflict has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. (2) Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. (3) Work family conflict has a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment. (4) Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment. (5) Organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. (6) Organizational commitment does not mediate the relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention. (7) Organizational commitment partially mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention.

KEYWORDS: Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, Turnover Intention, Work-Family Conflict.

INTRODUCTION

The performance of a company is determined by the conditions and behavior of the company's employees. A phenomenon that often occurs is that a company's performance can be disrupted, either directly or indirectly, by various employee behaviors that are difficult to prevent. One form of employee behavior is turnover intention.

Turnover intention is a situation where workers have a conscious intention or tendency to look for another job as an alternative in a different organization (Abdullah et al., 2012). According to Paissal et al. 2018, Turnover can be interpreted as the movement of workers out of the organization. Turnover can take the form of resignation, movement out of an organizational unit, dismissal or death of an organizational member. Employee turnover or employee turnover from an organization is the most important phenomenon in organizational life. There are times when employee turnover has a positive impact. However, most employee turnover has a negative impact on the organization, both in terms of costs and in terms of loss of time and opportunity to take advantage of opportunities (Ratnasari, 2015).

The general limitation for employee turnover is the cessation of an individual as a member of an organization accompanied by the provision of financial compensation (by the organization concerned). The termination of an individual as a member of an organization can be divided into two, namely voluntary release initiated by the employee and forced release initiated by the organization, including due to death and resignation at pressure.

Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant is one of the places to eat in Ubud, precisely on Jalan Raya Goa Gajah Peliatan Ubud. Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant is a fairly well-known place to eat and already has several branches in other areas of Bali and also outside Bali such as Jakarta. From the information obtained, the number of married employees is 38 people or 61.29%. According to the Manager of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant, Work-family conflict occurs where the time discipline applied here makes it difficult for employees to divide their time between work and family, conflicts with employee family obligations such as taking care of children, and religious ceremonies. There are employees who stop working because of the employee's own wishes. Employees who leave the organization because of their own wishes are because the employee is married, then has children (female employees), is pregnant, and there are employees who have found new jobs. Employee turnover arises because the employee finds it difficult to deal with work-family conflict, which is a dual role conflict that requires someone to divide their role between family and work. This dual role conflict triggers employees to focus on one role and then decide to resign from the organization. The same

phenomenon is based on the resultsof an initial survey conducted by the author at Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud which shows the employee turnover rate as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Employee entry and exit data At Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud2018 – 2022

Year	Initial Number of Employees	Number of Incoming Employees	Percentage	Number of Employee s Leaving	Percentage	Final Number of Employees
2018	66	5	7.57%	7	10.60%	64
2019	64	10	15.62%	3	4.68%	71
2020	71	0	0	5	7.04%	66
2021	66	0	0	6	9.09%	60
2022	60	9	15%	7	11.66%	62

Source: Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant

Based on Table 1.1, it can be seen that turnover intention tends to increase to reach 7 people in 2022 (11.66%), greater than the threshold level of 10%. As Ridlo (2012:5) states, turnover should not be more than 10% per year because it can cause losses to the organization, both in terms of costs and in terms of lost time and opportunities and can affect the work productivity of employees in an organization. According to the Manager of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant, the cause of turnover is because many employees want to get a new atmosphere and experience in another workplace after Covid-19. Apart from that, it is also caused by several other factors, namely age and marital status.

One of the causes of turnover intention is work-family conflict or what is usually called work-family conflict, where work-family conflictis considered an important issue in the current business world (Burke and El-Kot, 2010). Work- family conflict is a form of inter-role conflict thatoccurs when energy, time, or behavioral demandsfrom work roles conflict with family or personal life roles. Work-family conflict is becoming increasingly important in society because it has important consequences for work, non-work, and personal outcomes such as productivity, turnover,family well-being, health, and stress (Kossek et al., 2017). Work-family conflict that arises can trigger turnover intention (Alsam et al., 2013). Razaki and Rozana (2022) stated that work- family conflict has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention. Supported by research conducted by Noermijati et al. (2020) who stated that work-family conflict among female Papuan employees who work at PT Freeport Indonesia has a significant positive influence on turnover intention. This means that the higher the conflict a person feels, the higher the person's desire to leave the company.

Another cause of Turnover Intention is the job satisfaction factor. Robbins and Judge (2011) define Job Satisfaction as a positive feeling about a job, which is the impact or result of evaluation of various aspects of the job. Employee dissatisfaction can lead to undesirable work results, for example theft, looking for part-time work and can lead to employee absences from the workplace. Employee dissatisfaction also tends to give rise to behavioral practices of withdrawing from work such as leaving the company or resigning and considering opportunities to get another job.

The factor that is thought to influence employee turnover intention apart from work- family conflict and job satisfaction is organizational commitment as a mediator. This can be justified because apart from the direct influence of work-family conflict and job satisfaction on turnover intention, there is also an indirect influence through organizational commitment. Kweon et.al (2015) said that the factor that most influences turnover intention is organizational commitment. Furthermore, Baykara et.al (2021) succeeded in proving organizational commitment as a mediator between the relationship between work-family conflict and job satisfaction and turnover intention.

The desire to change employees at Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant which results in the employee leaving has a negative impact on the company, because it can create instability and uncertainty in the condition of the workforce. Turnover intention must be addressed as a phenomenon and human behavior that is very important in the company from an individual and social perspective. The employee's desire to move will have a significant impact on the company and the employee concerned. Ghayyur et al., (2012), Jehanzeb et al., (2013) and Maqsood et al., (2012), in their research confirmed that work-family conflict, job satisfaction and

organizational commitment are the causes of turnover intention, before employees decide to leave the organization. This phenomenon and series of problems are the background for the author to re-examine the influence of work-family conflict, job satisfaction on turnover intention and the role of organizational commitment as a mediator for Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees. So the author conducted research with the title "The Influence of Work-family Conflict and Job Satisfaction on Turnover Intention with Organizational Commitment as a Mediating Variable in Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud Employees".

THEORETICAL BASIS

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) proposed by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) states that behavior is influenced by attitudes through a careful and planned decision making process, and the impact is limited to three things; First, behavior is not determined so much by general attitudes but by specific attitudes towards something. Second, behavior is influenced not only by attitudes but also subjective norms. Third, attitudes towards a behavior together with subjective norms form an intention or intention to behave in a certain way. Based on TPB theory, it can be seen that turnover intention behavior can be measured through the intention to make a turnover. The essence of the TPB theory is that behavior is formed from intentions towards a behavior. Intention is a function of two basic determining factors, namely the individual's attitude towards behavior and the individual's perception of social pressure to carry out or not to carry out the behavior in question which is called subjective norm.

Traditional Turnover Theory

Traditional Turnover Theory This states that employees who have the intention to move (turnover intention) will show a negative attitude, namely employee performance decreases because employees feel dissatisfied with their current job and organization so they have thoughts of looking for work in another organization. This traditional turnover theory predicts employee turnover and retention behavior taken from job attitude factors such as "job satisfaction" and "organizational commitment". According to this theory, employees with high job satisfaction and organizational commitment are believed to not easily leave their positions in the company (Zhao and Liu, 2010).

Turnover Intention

Turnover Intention is an intention or desire that arises in an individual to do something. Meanwhile, Turnover Intention is the voluntary resignation of an employee from his place of work. Turnover Intention is a situation where workers have a conscious intention or tendency to look for another job as an alternative in a different organization (Abdullah et al., 2012). Novliadi (2007) and Mahdi et al., (2012) define Turnover Intention as an employee's tendency or intention to quit their job voluntarily according to their own choice. According to Paissal et al. 2018, Turnover can be interpreted as the movement of workers out of the organization. According to Lee and Zhao (2012: 870), the Turnover Intention indicator is thinking about leaving the organization (Thinking of quitting). Intention to look for alternative work (Intention to search for alternatives). Intention to leave the organization (Intention to quit).

Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment can be seen from an attitude of acceptance and strong belief in the company's values and goals. Robbins and Judge (2011) state that organizational commitment is a situation where an employee takes sides with the organization's goals and has the desire to maintain his or her membership in the organization. Robbins and Judge (2011) define organizational commitment as a condition where employees side with a particular company and its goals, and intend to maintain their membership in that company. According to Meyer and Allen (1993) in Satwari et al. (2016) indicators of organizational commitment are as follows. Affective commitment. Continued commitment.

Work-Family Conflict

Work-family conflict are two-way role demands where work demands interfere with family demands or responsibilities for example family caring responsibilities are interfered with work related responsibilities creating several undesirable outcomes such as stress, poor health, work related conflicts, absenteeism and turnover (Gahyyur and Jamal, 2012). Meanwhile, Kuswinaro and Indirawati (2021), stated that work-family conflict is a form of conflict between roles where the role has work and family pressure due to incompatibility in carrying out its role. According to Netemeyer, et al (1996) in Rahmawati (2015), indicators of work-family

conflict are: work pressure (work demand) and family pressure (family demand)

Job satisfaction

Robbins and Judge (2011) define Job Satisfaction as a positive feeling about a job, which is the impact or result of evaluation of various aspects of the job. Meanwhile, according to Wood et al. (1998) Job satisfaction is the extent to which an individual feels positive or negative about work, which is an emotional response to one's duties as well as physical and social conditions in the workplace. In simple terms, job satisfaction can be concluded as what makes people want and enjoy work because they feel happy doing their work (Sutrisno, 2014: 73). According to Luthans (2006) indicators of job satisfaction include: The job itself, salary, promotion opportunities, promotions, and co-workers.

HYPOTHESIS

- H1: Work-Family Conflict Has a Positive and Significant Influence on Turnover Intention.
- H2: Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.
- H3: Work-Family Conflict Variables Have a Negative and Significant Influence on Organizational Commitment.
- H4: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment.
- H5: Stating Organizational Commitment Has a Negative and Significant Influence on Turnover Intention.
- H6: Organizational Commitment Mediates the Effect of Work-Family Conflict on Turnover Intention.
- H7: Organizational Commitment Mediates the Effect of Job Satisfaction on Turnover Intention.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research used in this research is a quantitative approach, the research variables in this research are exogenous variables and endogenous variables. The dependent variable in this research is turnover intention and the mediating variable in this research is organizational commitment. The data collection techniques used in this research were observation, interviews and questionnaires. The data used is primary data and secondary data, with a research sample of 62 people. The data analysis technique used is SEM-Partial Least Square analysis. In analyzing the influence between exogenous and endogenous variables in this research, Partial Least Square (PLS) is used because this method does not require many assumptions, including the assumption of normality, and is popularly used in complex studies that are not supported by adequate theory. In testing the research instrument, IBM-SPSS software was used to test the validity and reliability of the results of distributing the questionnaire. Next, the data is processed using the SmartPLS application to determine the influence between the relationships between each variable.

ANALYSIS RESULTS

Structural Model Evaluation

Convergent validity is a criterion in measuring the validity of indicators that are reflexive. This evaluation is carried out by examining the outer loading coefficient of each indicator on the latent variable. An indicator is said to be valid if the outer loading coefficient is between 0.60 – 0.70, but for analyzes where the theory is not clear, an outer loading of 0.50 is recommended (Lathan and Ghazali, 2012: 78), and is significant at the alpha level of 0.05 or t- statistics 1.96.

Table 2. Convergent validity calculation results

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
X1.1 <- WORK FAMILY CONFLICT	0.904	0.028	32.425	0.000
X1.2 <- WORK FAMILY CONFLICT	0.848	0.041	20.551	0.000
X1.3 <- WORK FAMILY CONFLICT	0.941	0.012	77.757	0.000
X1.4 <- WORK FAMILY CONFLICT	0.896	0.026	34.188	0.000
X2.1 <- KEPUASAN KERJA	0.885	0.022	41.057	0.000
X2.2 <- KEPUASAN KERJA	0.821	0.035	23.516	0.000
X2.3 <- KEPUASAN KERJA	0.884	0.023	38.851	0.000
X2.4 <- KEPUASAN KERJA	0.875	0.025	34.404	0.000
X2.5 <- KEPUASAN KERJA	0.853	0.032	26.697	0.000
Y1.1 <- KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	0.802	0.083	9.717	0.000
Y1.2 <- KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	0.923	0.022	41.167	0.000
Y1.3 <- KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	0.813	0.078	10.395	0.000
Y2.1 <- TURNOVER INTENTION	0.782	0.058	13.527	0.000
Y2.2 <- TURNOVER INTENTION	0.892	0.021	41.562	0.000
Y2.3 <- TURNOVER INTENTION	0.883	0.028	31.666	0.000

Source: Calculation Results with the PLS Program

Table 2 shows that all the indicators that form the research construct have an outer loading value greater than 0.70 and are statistically significant at the 0.05 level so they are said to be valid based on the Convergent validity criteria.

Composite Reliability and Cronbach Alpha

A measurement can be said to be reliable if the composite reliability and Cronbach alpha have a value greater than 0.70. Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha are measurements of reliability between blocks of indicators in the research model.

Table 3. Composite Reliability Test and Cronbach Alpha

Matrix	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted...
	Cronbach's Alpha		Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
KEPUASAN KERJA	0.915		0.936	0.746
KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	0.806		0.884	0.719
TURNOVER INTENTION	0.814		0.889	0.729
WORK FAMILY CONFLICT	0.920		0.943	0.806

Source: Calculation Results with the PLS Program

Table 3 shows that the Composite reliability and Cronbach alpha values for all constructs have met the reliability requirements, namely with each index value being greater than 0.70. However, overall it has met the requirements for reliability.

Structural Model Evaluation Via R-Square (R2)

According to Chin (Lathan and Ghozali, 2012: 85), an R2 value of 0.67 is classified as a strong model, an R2 of 0.33 is a moderate model, and an R2 of 0.19 is classified as a weak model. The calculation results are shown in Table 5 below.

Table 4. R-Square (R2)

Matrix	R Square	R Square Adjusted
	R Square	R Square Adjusted
KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	0.082	0.051
TURNOVER INTENTION	0.630	0.611

Source: Calculation Results with the PLS Program

Table 5. Q2 Index

Total	Case1	Case2	Case3	Case4	Case5
	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)		
KEPUASAN KERJA	310.000	310.000			
KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	186.000	179.711	0.034		
TURNOVER INTENTION	186.000	105.675	0.432		
WORK FAMILY CONFLICT	248.000	248.000			

Source: PLS Calculation Results

The calculation results as shown in Table 3 show that the R-Square value of organizational commitment of 0.082 is included in the weak model criteria, meaning that work-family conflict and job satisfaction can explain variations in organizational commitment of 8.20 percent, while the remaining 91.80 percent is explained by variations in other variables outside the research model. Meanwhile, turnover intention has an R-Square index value of 0.63, including a strong model, meaning that work family conflict, job satisfaction and organizational commitment can explain variations in Turnover Intention of 63 percent while the remaining 37 percent is influenced by other constructs that are not analyzed in the estimation model.

The calculation results produce a Q2 value for organizational commitment = 0.034 (R2 taken from Table 5.9). Based on Lathan and Ghozali's criteria, it is included in the weak model criteria. Likewise, the Q2 value for turnover intention of 0.432 is also a strong model. This means that the global mathematical model built in this research has a high level of predictive accuracy.

Path Hypothesis Analysis and Testing

Evaluation of Structural Models via Goodness of Fit (GoF)

The criteria for the strength and weakness of a model based on GoF measurements according to Wetzels et al (Yamin, 2022), are as follows: 0.36 (GoF large)/model with high suitability, 0.25 (medium GoF), and 0.10 (GoF small). Akter et al (2011) suggest a cut off value of 0.36. The GoF formula is $\sqrt{A.R^2 * A.AVE} = \sqrt{0.351 * 0.782} = 0.524$ (R² is taken from Table 5.8 and the AVE value is from Table 5.7). These results indicate that the model built is a large model, meaning that the model meets the requirements as a fit model.

Table 6. Direct Effect

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O /STDEV)	P Values
KEPUASAN KERJA -> KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	-0.403	0.157	2.571	0.010
KEPUASAN KERJA -> TURNOVER INTENTION	0.442	0.114	3.889	0.000
KOMITMEN ORGANISASI -> TURNOVER INTENTION	-0.327	0.102	3.206	0.001
WORK FAMILY CONFLICT -> KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	0.237	0.171	1.386	0.166
WORK FAMILY CONFLICT -> TURNOVER INTENTION	0.277	0.088	3.161	0.002

Source: PLS Calculation Results

Table 7. Indirect Effects

	Original Sample (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O /STDEV)	P Values
KEPUASAN KERJA -> KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	-0.403	0.157	2.571	0.010
KEPUASAN KERJA -> TURNOVER INTENTION	0.574	0.100	5.726	0.000
KOMITMEN ORGANISASI -> TURNOVER INTENTION	-0.327	0.102	3.206	0.001
WORK FAMILY CONFLICT -> KOMITMEN ORGANISASI	0.237	0.171	1.386	0.166
WORK FAMILY CONFLICT -> TURNOVER INTENTION	0.199	0.095	2.096	0.037

Source: PLS Calculation Results

1. *Work family conflict* has a positive effect of 0.277 and is significant with a P value of 0.002 < 0.05 on turnover intention.
2. Job satisfaction has a positive effect of 0.442 and is significant with a P value of 0.000 < 0.05 on turnover intention.
3. *Work family conflict* has a positive effect of 0.237 and is not significant with a P Value of 0.166 > 0.05 on organizational commitment.
4. Job satisfaction has a negative effect of -0.403 and is significant with a P value of 0.010 < 0.05 on organizational commitment.
5. Organizational commitment has a negative effect of -0.327 and is significant with a P value of 0.001 < 0.05 on turnover intention.
6. Organizational commitment does not mediate the relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention. This can be seen from the direct relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention, which is significant with a P value of 0.037 < 0.05, while the indirect relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention through organizational commitment is not significant with a P value of 0.211 > 0.05.
7. Organizational commitment partially mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. This can be seen from the direct relationship between job satisfaction and Turnover Intention which is significant with a P Value of 0.000 < 0.05, as well as the indirect relationship of job satisfaction with Turnover Intention through organizational commitment is significant with a P Value of 0.026 < 0.05.

DISCUSSION

The Influence of Work-Family Conflict on Turnover Intention

Based on the results of the analysis regarding the influence of Work-family conflict (X1) on Turnover Intention (Y2), it shows that Work-Family Conflict has a positive effect of 0.277 and is significant with a P Value of $0.002 < 0.05$ on Turnover Intention. This means that the higher the conflict felt by Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees, the higher the employee's intention to leave the organization.

In this research, Work-Family Conflict is measured by the feelings of stress that employees sometimes feel at work, rest time, problems in the family and arriving late to work. rest time is the indicator that gets the lowest score, so companies need to pay attention to their employees' rest time. The employee's desire to leave Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud was due to the employee finding it difficult to divide their time between work and family, so the employee's desire to resign from work became higher after the conflict occurred.

The results of this research are in line with previous research conducted by Noermijati et al. (2020) who stated that work family conflict among female Papuan employees who work at PT Freeport Indonesia has a significant positive influence on turnover intention. This means that the higher the conflict a person feels, the higher the person's desire to leave the company. Kumar, et.al (2018) in their research also found that work-family conflict has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention among Generation Y employees in the hotel sector. Research conducted by Ganingtyas and Primadineska (2022) shows that work family conflict has a positive and significant effect on the turnover intention of the quality control department of PT Mataram Tunggal Garment. This is reinforced by research conducted by Razaki and Rozana (2022) which found that the work-family conflict variable had a positive and significant effect on turnover intention among Manufacturing Industry Employees. Apart from that, research conducted by Suardhika et al, (2023) also found that the work family conflict variable had a positive and significant effect on turnover intention among female employees in the Inka craft industry in Jembrana Regency. The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Turnover Intention

Based on the results of the analysis regarding the influence of job satisfaction (X2) on turnover intention (Y2), it shows that job satisfaction has a positive effect of 0.442 and is significant with a P value of $0.000 < 0.05$ on turnover intention. This means that the more job satisfaction felt by employees increases, the employee's desire to leave the organization will also increase.

In this research, job satisfaction is measured by the results of the job itself, salary, promotion opportunities, supervision and coworkers. Where promotion opportunities and co-workers get the lowest score among other indicators, while the salary indicator gets the highest score. This means that even though the employees of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud are satisfied with the salaries provided by the organization, the employees are less satisfied with the lack of promotional opportunities there and co-workers who are less able to collaborate with them at work so that the employees of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud have the desire to look for work. other.

The results of this research are not in line with research conducted by Rizki and Juhaeti (2022) who examined PT Maintenance Section Employees. Sidomulyo Selaras Tbk. which states that job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention. What companies should do is increase job satisfaction so that employees can make even more optimal contributions to the company. So it can prevent unwanted turnover intention which can be detrimental to the company. The same research results were also found by Sastrawan et al (2022), Masyhuni (2023) and Dwiyantri et al. (2023) who found that job satisfaction had a negative and significant effect on turnover intention.

The Influence of Work-family Conflict on Organizational Commitment

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of work-family conflict (X1) on organizational commitment (Y1), it shows that work family conflict has a positive effect of 0.237 and is not significant with a P value of $0.166 > 0.05$ on organizational commitment. This means that the increasing work family conflict felt by Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees is not necessarily able to increase employee organizational commitment.

In this research, Work-Family Conflict is measured by the feelings of stress that employees sometimes feel at work, rest time, problems in the family and arriving late to work. rest time is the indicator that gets the lowest score, so companies need to pay attention to their employees' rest time. Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees who experience Work-Family Conflict can be seen from the decline in employee loyalty and commitment to the organization, such as those who arrive late, dress untidily and

there are employees who have sullen faces when serving customers.

The results of this research are not in line with research conducted by Fintariasari et al (2020) which found that the work-family conflict variable had a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment. Dharsana and Wibawa (2020) in their research also found that work-family conflict has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment among PT employees. Pacific Express Garment Denpasar. The same results were also found by Hidayati, et al (2021) where the work-family conflict variable had a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment in health workers at RSU Latersia Binjai, also supported by research from Sidimantra and Netra (2020) which stated that work-family conflict has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment in the Kerobokan Traditional Village LPD. Likewise, research from Az-Zahra (2023) in his research found that work-family conflict had a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment among employees in the production department of PT. Lokatex Pekalongan. The higher level of work-family conflict can reduce organizational commitment in employees.

The Influence of Job Satisfaction on Organizational Commitment

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of job satisfaction (X2) on organizational commitment (Y1), it shows that job satisfaction has a negative effect of -0.403 and is significant with a P value of $0.010 < 0.05$ on organizational commitment. This means that the more job satisfaction felt by Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees increases, the organizational commitment actually decreases. In this research, job satisfaction is measured by the results of the job itself, salary, promotion opportunities, supervision and coworkers. Where promotion opportunities and co-workers get the lowest score among other indicators, while the salary indicator gets the highest score. This means that even though the employees of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud are satisfied with the salaries provided by the company, the employees are less satisfied with the lack of promotional opportunities there and co-workers who are less able to collaborate with them in their work, which causes the commitment and loyalty of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees towards organization declines. Apart from that, employee organizational commitment decreases because there are employees who want to get new jobs and increase their career path.

The results of this research are not in line with research conducted by Yousef (2017) where in his research on regional government in Saudi Arabia, it was stated that job satisfaction had a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. Sitiari and Widari (2020) in their research on Puri Santrian employees succeeded in proving that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. The results of the same research were also carried out by Herawati et al. (2022) on Grand Rohan Jogja employees proves that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment. Companies should be sensitive to employee needs so that employees feel satisfied and have high organizational commitment. Manobawa (2022) also succeeded in showing that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on organizational commitment among employees of The Kawi Resort By Pramana Experience Tampaksiring. Also supported by research results from Sastrawan et al. (2022) at Auto 2000 in the Sanur Denpasar Branch which stated that job satisfaction had a significant positive effect on organizational commitment. Those who are satisfied with their salary, promotions, coworkers and job security aspects will be more willing to stay with their current department.

The Influence of Organizational Commitment on Turnover Intention

Based on the results of the analysis of the influence of organizational commitment (Y1) on Turnover Intention (Y2), organizational commitment has a negative effect of -0.327 and is significant with a P Value of $0.001 < 0.05$ on turnover intention. This means that as the organizational commitment of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees increases, the employee's desire to leave the organization decreases.

In this study, organizational commitment is measured by Affective commitment. When an employee has high affective commitment, the employee will remain in an organization because the employee really wants that. Normative commitment is the employee's feelings about the obligations that must be met. done for the organization, and this action is something that should be done. Continuance commitment Continuance commitment is a hard feeling to leave an organization due to the need to survive considering the costs of leaving the organization. In this research, organizational commitment is most dominantly explained by the Continuance Commitment indicator. This means that employees of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud find it difficult to find new jobs with their current income.

The results of this research are in line with research conducted by Rizki and Juhaeti (2022) in their research proving that

organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention among Sidomulyo Selaras Tbk employees. Jakarta. So the higher the organizational commitment felt by employees, the lower the employee's intention to leave the company. The same results were also found by Hikmah and Nurweni (2022) that organizational commitment had a negative and significant effect on turnover intention among Troy Company employees in Yogyakarta. The higher the level of organizational commitment that employees have, the lower the level of employee turnover intention.

The Role of Organizational Commitment in Mediating the Influence of Work-Family Conflict on Turnover Intention

Organizational commitment does not mediate the relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention. This can be seen from the direct relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention which is significant with a P Value of $0.037 < 0.05$, while the indirect relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention through organizational commitment is not significant with a P Value of $0.211 > 0.05$. The meaning of the role of mediation here shows that the influence of work family conflict on turnover intention has not been able to be conveyed properly by organizational commitment, in other words organizational commitment does not mediate the relationship between Work-Family Conflict and Turnover Intention among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees.

This research is not in line with research conducted by Bayraka et.al (2021) which proves that organizational commitment is able to mediate the relationship between work-family conflict and turnover intention. Research by Firmanzah, et al. (2020), Fintariasari, et al. (2020) and Hermawati, et al (2022) also prove that organizational commitment is able to mediate the relationship between work-family conflict and turnover intention.

The Role of Organizational Commitment in Mediating the Influence of Job Satisfaction on Turnover Intention

Organizational commitment partially mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention. This can be seen from the direct relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention which is significant with a P Value of $0.000 < 0.05$, as well as the indirect relationship of job satisfaction with turnover intention through organizational commitment is significant with a P Value of $0.026 < 0.05$. This means that apart from organizational commitment there are other constructs that mediate job satisfaction in increasing turnover intention, such as discipline, regulations and compensation.

This research is in line with research conducted by Surya and Utama (2020) which proves that organizational commitment is able to mediate job satisfaction and employee turnover intention. This is also not in line with research conducted by Sastrawan et al. (2022), Manobawa (2022), Utami and Rahmawati (2022) and Suwiningtyas et al. (2023) which stated that job satisfaction influences turnover intention with the role of organizational commitment as a mediator.

THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as stated by Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) stated that the high level of employee turnover in the hospitality industry can be seen from how much desire or intention to move employees of an organization or company have. Turnover intention needs to be identified more quickly so that employees do not leave the company. In this research, what influences turnover intention is organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and work-family conflict. In this research, the most dominant reflection of employee turnover intention is the employee's intention to look for a new job, lack of promotional opportunities and workload that takes up employee rest time. To reduce the level of employee turnover intention requires strong organizational commitment.

Commitment is needed by organizations so that competent human resources in the organization can be well maintained and maintained (Suparman, 2007). In this research, the most dominant reflection of organizational commitment in employees is that employees feel proud to be part of the organization and the employee's attitude of loyalty and commitment to the organization.

Job satisfaction can influence the strength of employee organizational commitment. In this research, job satisfaction is most dominantly reflected in employee satisfaction with the work provided and employee satisfaction with the salary provided by the organization. Employee job satisfaction is an important aspect that needs to be considered. If employee job satisfaction is met, they will tend to have motivation to work, have high commitment and perform well.

Work-family conflict is one of the factors that causes turnover. In this research, work-family conflict is most dominantly reflected in the workload that takes up employee rest time, so companies need to pay attention to their employees' rest time.

PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on the findings of this research, it is proven that sufficient job satisfaction among employees still influences turnover intention. It must be realized that in the tourism industry, the employee turnover rate is quite high. Because many new hotels and restaurants are emerging, competition is also increasing. Every employee also wants a good career path so many employees want to move in and out of the organization. Management perceives that training costs are also large but the results are not necessarily optimal. So, the management of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud must create a good strategy to prevent competent employees from leaving the company. By further increasing job satisfaction and organizational commitment to employees.

RESEARCH LIMITATIONS

The method for filling out the questionnaire is in the form of a self-administered survey which allows respondents to fill in, allowing respondents to experience errors in their own perception of the questionnaire, namely the statements in the questionnaire, which may cause the respondent's answers to not be as expected.

Regarding the answers given by respondents to question items regarding work-family conflict, job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intention in the questionnaire in this research, of course the answers given by respondents will be greatly influenced by the character, condition and understanding of each individual. When respondents answer questionnaire questions in this research, there is a possibility that respondents answer questions that are not in accordance with the actual facts.

The number of variables in this research only uses 3 variables to measure turnover intention, including work-family conflict, job satisfaction and organizational commitment, while other research variables that influence turnover intention are not used in this research.

CONCLUSION

1. *Work family conflict* has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees. This means that the more work family conflict felt by employees increases, the employee's desire to leave the organization will increase.
2. Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on turnover intention among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees. This means that the more job satisfaction felt by employees increases, the employee's desire to leave the organization will also increase.
3. *Work family conflict* has a positive and insignificant effect on organizational commitment among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees. This means that the increasing work family conflict felt by employees does not necessarily increase employee organizational commitment.
4. Job satisfaction has a negative and significant effect on organizational commitment among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees. This means that the more job satisfaction felt by employees increases, the employee's organizational commitment actually decreases.
5. Organizational commitment has a negative and significant effect on turnover intention among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees. This means that as employees' organizational commitment increases, their desire to leave the organization decreases.
6. Organizational commitment does not mediate the relationship between work family conflict and turnover intention among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees.
7. Organizational commitment partially mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and turnover intention among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees.

SUGGESTION

1. In the work-family conflict variable, rest time is the indicator that gets the lowest score, so companies need to pay attention to the rest time of their employees by increasing the rest time by 15 minutes to 30 minutes from the usual hours, and giving morning shifts before employees have their holidays and giving afternoon shifts after employees holidays so employees can get more rest time.

2. Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud should pay more attention to the job satisfaction of its employees, because this variable has the highest influence on overcoming employee turnover. This can be done by expanding promotional opportunities that are valued by employees and cooperation between teams is further enhanced by establishing good relationships between employees, building a sense of trust between employees, exercising and hanging out together, appreciation with rewards and celebrations. Promotion opportunities at Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud can be expanded by giving promotions to employees who are loyal to the company or have a long service period at the company.
3. The overall organizational commitment of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees is in the sufficient category, so the management of Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud must further increase employee organizational commitment in order to reduce the level of turnover intention among Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud employees by making employees happy to spend the rest of their career in this company. With employees feeling happy to spend the rest of their careers at Bebek Tepi Sawah Restaurant Ubud, indirectly they will not feel pressured by the existing regulations in the company and will reduce their intention to change jobs.
4. For further research, it is necessary to examine job stress, workload and other alternative jobs as mediating variables to identify turnover intention. This is necessary to determine work-family conflict, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment and their influence on turnover intention with work stress, workload and other job alternatives as variables that mediate the influence between these variables.

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